

Conference Abstract

The IUCN-SSC Cave Invertebrate Specialist Group

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Abstract

The Cave Invertebrate Specialist Group, an IUCN Species Survival Commission, is a group of 80 taxonomists, biospeleologists, ecologists, and conservation biologists. Since 2014, our objectives have been to: (1) conserve subterranean habitats, and address one of the largest lacunas in conservation biology – the protection of sensitive cave and subterranean invertebrate populations; (2) conduct IUCN Red List evaluations for imperiled and/or narrow range endemic species; (3) encourage comprehensive baseline biodiversity surveys, in particular to determine the proportion of unknown biodiversity yet to be discovered; and, (4) provide collaborative opportunities with the business sector for conducting Environmental and Social Impact Assessments, Biodiversity Action Plans, and site and species management plans. We will our accomplishments over the past four years including growth of membership, the number of Red List evaluations conducted and the total number of species recognized as a conservation priority.

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